

Notes on the orb-web spiders of Mpetsane Conservancy Estate in the Free State (Arachnida: Araneae) - part 2

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides notes on the behaviour of species of the families Araneidae and Tetragnathidae presently protected at Mpetsane Conservation Estate in the Free State. A variety of webs were observed that include true orb-webs, adapted orb-webs and reduced orb-webs.

Key words: Araneidae, diversity, grasslands, Tetragnathidae

INTRODUCTION

In Africa, the Grassland Biome is largely limited to the central plateau of South Africa, Lesotho and parts of Swaziland (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2013). A total of 63 families, 274 genera and 789 described species have been documented from the Grassland Biome to date (Haddad *et al.* 2013). Different species are adapted to particular microhabitats within grasslands, either living on the ground, on grasses or on the foliage of woody plants, with few species abundant in multiple strata (Haddad *et al.* 2013).

Observations showed that there are several unique orb-web spiders at the Mpetsane Conservation Estate (MCE) in the Free State Province, South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2021). These species have special adaptations in body form, colour, and web and retreat construction. Grasses are extensively used as frameworks for web construction, as retreats, or to attach their eggs sacs. Many orb-web species are nocturnal, to escape the high daytime temperatures in the summer, predators like birds, and to utilize the large quantity of insects available at night. These species have special adaptations in shape and colour that make them cryptic on grass during the day. By preying on insects and even other arachnids, spiders are an important link in the grassland food web.

This report was not conceived as a scientific study as such, but is the result of observations and a photographic survey undertaken regularly over a 14-year period in a grassland fragment at MCE (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2021). No quantitative methods were used and the main focus was hand searching and observations on the web inhabitants. More than 2000 photographs of the arachnids of MCE were taken over the years.

The use of a web to capture prey is assumed to have developed long after spiders came into existence, and it took more than 200 million years for the first orb-web to appear. The great diversity in web types suggests that this strategy is very successful. The webs of spiders are highly specialised structures that might be considered an extension of the spider's tactile sense organs. Although some webs may seem to be a chaotic arrangement of silk threads, all threads serve a definite purpose. The following orb-web types are known:

- adapted orb-webs – adapted in shape to catch a certain group of prey e.g. moths.
- reduced orb-webs, which include “webs” that consist of only of a few strands of silk with more active involvement of the spiders in the hunting process.
- typical orb-webs: diurnal and nocturnal.

STUDY AREA

The survey was carried out in grassland at the Mpetsane Conservation Estate (MCE) that is situated in the Eastern Free State highlands, some 14 km from Clocolan (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2021). Of the 138 species known from the area, the most species-rich family is the Araneidae (21 spp.) (Table 1). A large number of the species have been photographed and the diverse orb-web spiders

Figure 1: Orb-web at MCE (Photo: A. Jones)

Table 1: Orb-web species sampled from Mpetsane Conservation Estate

ARANEIDAE

- Argiope aurocineta* Pocock, 1898 (Fig. 14)
Argiope australis (Walckenaer, 1805) (Figs 11, 12, 15)
Argiope lobata (Pallas, 1772) (Fig. 13)
Cyclosa insulana (Costa, 1834) (Fig. 26)
Cyrtarachne ixoides (Simon, 1870) (Figs 5-7)
Cyrtophora citricola (Forsskål, 1775) (Figs 1-4)
Kilima decens (Blackwall, 1866) (Fig. 20)
Larinia bifida Tullgren, 1910 (Fig. 22)
Neoscona blondeli (Simon, 1885) (Fig. 23)
Neoscona moreli (Vinson, 1863) (Fig. 21)
Neoscona subfusca (C.L. Koch, 1837) (Fig. 24)
Neoscona triangula (Keyserling, 1864) (Fig. 25)
Pycnantha tribulus (Fabricius, 1781) (Figs 8-10)
Trichonephila fenestrata Thorell, 1859 (Fig. 17)
Trichonephila senegalensis annulata (Thorell, 1859) (Figs 18-19)

TETRAGNATHIDAE

- Leucauge festiva* (Blackwall, 1866) (Figs 27-29)
Tetragnatha demissa L. Koch, 1872 (Fig. 26)

1. ADAPTED ORB-WEBS

***Cyrtophora citricola*:** The tropical tent-web spiders are represented by a single cosmopolitan species, *Cyrtophora citricola*, which was commonly found at MCE. They make a modified orb-web consisting of a horizontal orb with a very tightly woven mesh, and a tight, permanent, non-sticky spiral that is either dome- or bowl-shaped (Figs 1-3). The web is semi-permanent, with the hub open and irregular in shape and size. They are commonly found in grasslands (Francini et al. 2013). The open hub serves as a passage between the upper and lower levels of the web. The webs are usually arranged one above the other, with irregular barrier webs located above the layered webs (Figs 1-3). The adults sometimes build a retreat among dry leaves and egg sacs in the web. The spiders are diurnal and tend to stay in the hub, operating from beneath the orb-web. Flying insects are initially caught in the upper webbing, while the spider waits to kill the prey once it lands on the orb-web. They repair their webs every day and renew the entire web from time to time. When disturbed, they immediately drop out of the web. At the same time, the colour pattern of the abdomen changes rapidly so that the spider blends in with its immediate background.

On two occasions, 14 April 2018 and 21 March 2021, very high densities of juveniles were observed at MCE. Their tent webs covered large areas (Fig. 4).

Figures 1-4. *Cyrtophora citricola* tropical tent-webs.

***Cyrtarachne ixoides*:** The first record of the bird-dropping spider *Cyrtarachne ixoides* from South Africa was discovered in the garden at MCE (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones 2008). This orb-weaving spider of the subfamily Cyrtarachninae (Araneidae) (Fig. 5) is known to construct another type of adapted orb-web to catch Lepidopteran prey, known as a “spanning-thread web” (Figs 6-7). This is basically an orb-web, but the web diameter, sticky spiral spacing and viscid thread diameter differs from that of typical orb-webs. The viscid threads are studded with large droplets that are very effective to catch prey coming in contact with them. Each of the short threads between the radii is known as a spanning thread, and is unique in that it breaks when prey comes in contact with it. The prey fly into the web, get stuck to a viscid thread, the thread breaks, and the spider pulls the prey up to the centre of the web to feed. Each of the spanning threads are good to only capture one prey item. It was suggested that the low-shear joint reduces the momentum of the prey and increases the likelihood of being captured.

During the day, the spider rests on nearby vegetation, mimicking bird-droppings. Some studies found that 92% of the prey was moths. Several photographs of the Clocolan bird dropping spider are available and most of the prey are moths, but the odd other insect is also captured, such as crane flies (Diptera: Tipulidae).

Figures 5-7. *Cyrtarachne ixoides* female and web.

2. REDUCED ORB-WEBS

***Pycnacantha tribulus*:** The hedgehog spiders are rare inhabitants of the Grassland Biome and are occasionally found in grasses and low vegetation. Their spiky bodies and creamy-brown body allow the spiders to blend in with grass, particularly *Themeda* and *Cymbopogon* species that have a spiky inflorescence (Fig. 8). The spiders rest on the vegetation during the day, and in the evening spin a reduced orb-web in the form of a triangular trapezium between two adjacent grass stems. Here they hang upside down (Figs 9-10), capturing flying moths when within striking range, using the front two pairs of legs (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 1996). These spiders are suspected to produce molecules that mimic female moth pheromones that attract male moths. Egg sacs are attached to vegetation. The species is very rare and has only been observed twice in 14 years at MCE.

Figures 8-10. *Pycnacantha tribulus* female.

3. TYPICAL ORB-WEBBS

DIURNAL SPECIES

Argiope spp.: *Argiope* spp. are common grass-dwellers, and three species have been recorded from MCE: *Argiope australis* (butter spider, or black and yellow banded spider); *A. lobata* (black spot banded spider) and *A. aurocincta* (black banded orb-web spider). The first two species are commonly found at MCE. They spin a typical orb-web in the grass, with anchor threads attached to the grass. Sometimes they will attach zigzagging white stabilimentum bands that radiate from the centre. The webs are built in tall grass and low shrubs in sunny areas, and the orientation of their webs varies seasonally in relation to the midday angle of the sun. Their webs are made in a variety of habitats, in any vegetation sturdy enough to bear the weight of the web and the spider. A variety of flying and jumping insects are snared in the web, including bees, flies and grasshoppers. The prey is usually wrapped in silk through rapid movements of the hind legs, after which it is bitten and fed upon. They are active during the day when the spider hangs in the centre of the web, facing downwards. They use the same web for long periods, and as the sticky silk dries or becomes torn the web is regularly removed and replaced. Most of the webs they make are large, at least 500 mm wide with some even larger. The males have their own webs, and only a few males were found together with a female on her web.

Figures 13-14. Female *Argiope lobata* (13) and *A. aurocincta* (14).

After some rain in April 2012, we discovered an “*Argiope* city” in the northern area of MCE, with between 50-60 spider webs present in the bushes. It was amazing that there were so many spiders present just in this one location on the farm, and all *Argiope australis*. Normally they are found throughout the estate. They had obviously found a good food source in this area, as high numbers of grasshoppers (Orthoptera: Acrididae: *Truxalis* sp.) were found in most webs (Jones 2012). AJ recalls: “I have often wondered how they move around, as we do have many *Argiope* here. Clearly they cannot balloon, but I was lucky enough to find one female clambering through the grassland (this was obviously very difficult for her, unlike smaller species). It took her some 5 minutes to cover 3 metres, yet she was intent on her route and would have to move several hundred metres to another site, where she would then climb grass stalks and construct another web, and set herself up once again... truly an impressive display.”

Just recently, A.J. observed a large female creating a web on top of a 1.8 metre high Wild Asparagus bush (*Asparagus laricinus*). She remained there for some 73 days, feeding regularly on moths mainly, eventually she became thinner and inactive and then disappeared.

Figure 11-12. *Argiope australis*, female (11) and male (12).

Fig. 15. *Argiope australis* eating a grasshopper.

Trichonephila spp.: The golden orb-web spiders build large (1–1.5 m) orb-webs between trees and shrubs. The viscid spiral of the web is yellowish and the radii are pulled out of their direct course to give it a notched appearance. The supporting lines are very strong and some resistance is felt when one wanders into them. The spiders make use of the same web over long periods, replacing only the viscid lines. In the older spiders the web may only be half a circle, while in the younger individuals the orb is more complete. Two species have been recorded from MCE: *Trichonephila fenestrata* (Fig. 16) and *T. senegalensis annulata* (Fig. 17).

Figures 16–17. Female *Trichonephila fenestrata* (16) and *T. senegalensis annulata* (17).

During April 2021, a large aggregation of more than 50 females congregated in a clump of trees (*Celtis africana*, *Diospyros lyciodes*, *Kigellaria africana* and *Cussonia paniculata*), where they created a mass of huge webs, with some lines 5 m high x 7 m wide. Their webs were just centimetres apart, yet they showed no aggression to each other. In fact, they appeared to give each other space when a prey was captured and eaten. In other bushes and small trees nearby the same phenomenon was observed; mixed species in very close company, again large groups of webs. Altogether well over 100 spiders had gathered in this part of the mountain. They remained there for over 60 days, and despite some heavy rain storms and windy days little damage was done to their webs, and they all appeared to have captured plenty of prey items: bees, flies, moths, and even a dragonfly. What was fascinating was their harmonious tolerance of each other. Several males were observed moving from web to web amongst the females (Fig. 18).

Figure 18. Numerous *Trichonephila senegalensis annulata* in an aggregation of webs.

NOCTURNAL SPECIES

A large number of species live exclusively on grass blades and can be easily recognised by their elongated bodies and long, thin legs. Their colour varies from cream to fawn to green and many species have darker longitudinal stripes over the length of their bodies that closely resemble the main vein of a blade of grass. Their often cryptic colouration, and the fact that the legs are held parallel to the body axis when resting, make many of them difficult to detect. The species that live on grass inflorescences are sometimes spiny in appearance. Their large orb-webs are usually made in grass in the early evening, mainly at sundown when moths take flight. Often the webs remain intact during the day and the spiders use the same web for days, feeding on flying insects.

Kilima decens are typical grassland species. They are very numerous at MCE. Their large orb-webs are usually made in grass at early evening mainly at sundown when moths take flight (Fig. 19).

Figure 19. *Kilima decens* female.

Neoscona moreli is another very common grassland species that makes its web at night and removes it early in the morning. They are predators of a variety of insects. The scalloped abdominal pattern differs from the other grass species (Fig. 20), and the abdomen is more elongate than other members of the genus *Neoscona*.

Figures 20–21. *Neoscona moreli* (20) and *Larinia bifida* (21) females.

Larinia bifida is a typical grassland orb-web species, resembling grass in shape and colour. They are not easily seen during the day while resting on grass. When at rest they stretch their body and legs along a blade of grass. The orb-webs are made at night and removed early in the morning.

Three other species of hairy field spiders of the genus *Neoscona* are very common in grass and construct their orb-webs late in the afternoon or early evening, dismantling them in the morning. These spiders are creamy-brown with varied markings (Figs 22-24).

Fig. 22. *Neoscona blondeli* female.

Fig. 23. *Neoscona subfusca* female.

Fig. 24. *Neoscona triangula* female.

Cyclosa insulana (Fig. 25) usually build their webs in shrubs and trees, but may sometimes also be abundant in grass. The stabilimentum consists mainly of the remains of captured prey, which are attached in a vertical line in the centre of the web. The spiders take up a position in line with the stabilimentum, hence their common name, garbage-line spiders.

Fig. 25. *Cyclosa insulana* female.

Tetragnatha demissa (Fig. 26) occupy tall reeds and grasses where they usually construct orb-webs between vegetation near or horizontally over streams, rivers, dams and ponds. In *Tetragnatha* the webs are short-lived, as they are taken down and digested daily or even more frequently, and are usually horizontally oriented.

Fig. 26. *Tetragnatha demissa* female.

Leucauge festiva are brightly coloured spiders (Figs 28, 29) that spin their large orb-webs both in the morning and during the day (Fig. 27), and sometimes reuse the frame and anchor lines. The inclination of the webs varies from vertical to horizontal, but is most often at a sharp angle to the ground. The hub is open, with clear, widely spaced viscid spirals (15–30). Amazingly, several webs with more than one occupant, even three spiders in a single web together, were observed, giving each spider a part of the web to “use”. Another interesting sight- ing was that several spiders were found up on the mountain, far from any water source.

Figures 27-29. *Leucauge festiva* female web (27) and habitus (28, 29).

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